

Practice Abstract no. 38

Industry & food system actors' views on the challenges with the use of AI in the food system

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

This practice abstract discusses industry & food system actors' views on the main challenges regarding the use of AI in the food system.

- **Data and information quality:** a concern raised by participants is the risk of generating and disseminating false data among actors. This practice severely undermines data quality and reliability. Compounding this challenge is the potential lack of specialised mechanisms for data quality control, highlighting the critical necessity for robust validation and quality assurance processes.
- **Trust and management:** a challenge linked to the still existing lack of trust in AI-based systems was noted. This might be more prominent in actors with a lower degree of technological literacy. In general, participants suggested a need for better governance and oversight.
- **Complementing knowledge and environmental impact:** there was a general agreement on AI's high value and abundant opportunities, but there is a recurrent need to complement and validate AI-based information with other forms of knowledge, including human, real-life expertise.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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